

Membrane Selectivity and Reflection Coefficient

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Permeation of nonelectrolyte and electrolyte solutions in the light of non-equilibrium thermodynamic theory developed by Katchalsky *et al.* has been examined. The analysis shows that selectivity of an ideally semipermeable membrane can be adequately expressed in terms of reflection coefficient even when interaction between permeating solute and solvent is considered.

USING formal non-equilibrium thermodynamic treatment Katchalsky *et al.*¹ have shown that the ability of a membrane to discriminate between a solute and a solvent can be adequately expressed in terms of reflection coefficient, earlier defined by Stavermann². The desirability of this coefficient for the description of membrane systems has been widely accepted. It has been used for the expression of the selectivity of natural and artificially prepared membranes³⁻⁵. When two solutions of unequal concentrations are separated by a membrane, the solute and the solvent are driven by the differences in their chemical potentials acting across the membrane. It has been shown that the entropy production, ϕ , in this case may be expressed as⁶

$$\phi = J_s \Delta \mu_s + J_w \Delta \mu_w \quad \dots (1)$$

J_s and J_w denote solute and solvent flux and $\Delta \mu_s$ and $\Delta \mu_w$, are differences in their chemical potentials respectively. The entropy production has alternatively been expressed in the following manner.

$$\phi = J_v \Delta P + J_D \Delta \pi \quad \dots (2)$$

where

$$J_v = J_s \bar{V}_s + J_w \bar{V}_w \quad \dots (3)$$

$$J_D = \frac{J_s}{\bar{C}_s} - J_w V_w \quad \dots (4)$$

ΔP and $\Delta \pi$ respectively denote difference in hydrostatic pressure and osmotic pressure. $\bar{V}_s$ and $\bar{V}_w$ denote partial molar volumes of solute and solvent, $\bar{C}_s$ is the numerical average of the concentration of the solute on the two sides of the membrane. The fluxes J_v and J_D may be expressed in terms of the ΔP and $\Delta \pi$ with the help of the phenomenological equations

$$J_v = L_{11} \Delta P + L_{12} \Delta \pi$$

$$J_D = L_{21} \Delta P + L_{22} \Delta \pi$$

L 's are phenomenological coefficients. The reflection coefficient, σ , is defined as

$$\sigma = - \left[\frac{L_{12}}{L_{11}} \right]_{J_v=0}$$

The magnitude of reflection coefficient depends on the nature of the membrane and the permeating species. An ideally semipermeable membrane has $\sigma = 1$. For a membrane which permits passage to the solute particles alongwith the solvent molecules, reflection coefficient is always less than unity and $\sigma = 0$ in case of a membrane which does not discriminate at all between the permeating solute and solvent.

Recently Srivastava *et al.*⁷ questioned the applicability of this approach and have shown that σ need not necessarily be equal to one in the case of an ideally semipermeable membrane which is capable of completely reflecting the solute if the solute and solvent interacted while being transported through the membrane.

It, however, easily follows from their treatment that if equation (23) (Ref. 7) is substituted in equations (26)-(29) (Ref. 7), one gets

$$\sigma = - \left[\frac{L_{12}}{L_{11}} \right]_{J_v=0} = 1$$

when no solute flux occurs. The conclusion that Srivastava *et al.*⁷ arrived at, is, therefore, not valid.

We now examine the permeation of an electrolyte solution wherein interaction between the solute and the solvent is involved. Suppose the electrolyte produces ions 1 and 2 when it dissociates in water. The expression for the entropy production in this case has been shown to be⁸

$$\phi = J_1 \Delta \mu_1 + J_2 \Delta \mu_2 + J_w \Delta \mu_s \quad \dots (5)$$

$\Delta \mu_1$ and $\Delta \mu_2$ denote difference in electrochemical potentials of ions 1 and 2. The solute flux J_s , may

be expressed in terms of ionic fluxes, J_1 and J_2 as it is possible to write equation (8) as

$$J_s = \frac{J_1}{\nu_1} = \frac{J_2}{\nu_2} \quad \dots (6)$$

when no current flow is involved. ν_1 and ν_2 are the number of cations and anions produced from one molecule of the electrolyte. The chemical potentials of the solute and those of ions are related as⁹

$$\nu_1 \Delta \mu_1 + \nu_2 \Delta \mu_2 = \Delta \mu_s \quad \dots (7)$$

Using equations (6) and (7), equation (5) becomes identical with the equation (1) and hence

$$\sigma = - \left[\frac{L_{12}}{L_{11}} \right]_{J_s=0} = 1$$

when $J_s = 0$.

We, therefore, conclude that criterion developed by Katchalsky *et al.*¹ for the description of selectivity of ideally semipermeable membranes is adequate even when interaction between the permeating solute and solvent is considered.

Permeation of Solute Mixture Solutions

It is known¹⁰ that in living systems permeation of a number of substances such as sugars, aminoacids etc., with varying degrees of restriction occurs through cell membrane. It is, therefore, of interest to examine the possibility of description of the selectivity of such complicated systems in terms of the reflection coefficients.

Let us consider first the permeation of a solution containing solutes 1 and 2, when interaction between various constituents of the solution is completely ignored. It is possible to write down the volumetric flux J_v , as

$$J_v = \left[\frac{\partial(J_s)_1}{\partial(\Delta\mu)_1} (\Delta\mu_s)_1 \right] (\bar{V}_s)_1 + \left[\frac{\partial(J_s)_2}{\partial(\Delta\mu)_2} (\Delta\mu_s)_2 \right] (\bar{V}_s)_2 + \left[\frac{\partial J_\omega}{\partial \Delta \mu_\omega} \cdot \Delta \mu_\omega \right] \bar{V}_\omega \quad \dots (8)$$

Since

$$\left. \begin{aligned} (\Delta\mu_s)_1 &= (\bar{V}_s)_1 \Delta P + \frac{(\Delta\pi)_1}{(C_s^-)_1} \\ (\Delta\mu_s)_2 &= (\bar{V}_s)_2 \Delta P + \frac{(\Delta\pi)_2}{(C_s^-)_2} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad \dots (9)$$

and

$$\Delta \mu_\omega = V_\omega (\Delta P - \Delta \pi)$$

$$J_v = \left[(\bar{V}_s)_1^2 \frac{\partial(J_s)_1}{\partial(\Delta\mu_s)_1} + (\bar{V}_s)_2^2 \frac{\partial(J_s)_2}{\partial(\Delta\mu_s)_2} + \bar{V}_\omega^2 \frac{\partial(J_\omega)}{\partial(\Delta\mu_\omega)} \right] \Delta P + \left[\frac{(\bar{V}_s)_1}{(C_s^-)_1} \frac{\partial(J_s)_1}{\partial(\Delta\mu_s)_1} - \bar{V}_\omega^2 \frac{\Delta C}{2\Delta C_1} \frac{\partial J_\omega}{\partial \Delta \mu_\omega} \right] \Delta \pi_1 + \left[\frac{(\bar{V}_s)_2}{(C_s^-)_2} \frac{\partial(J_s)_2}{\partial(\Delta\mu_s)_2} - \bar{V}_\omega^2 \frac{\Delta C}{2\Delta C_2} \frac{\partial J_\omega}{\partial \Delta \mu_\omega} \right] \Delta \pi_2 \quad \dots (10)$$

where the relations

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta \bar{\pi}_i &= RT \Delta C_i \\ \frac{\Delta \pi}{\Delta C} &= \frac{(\Delta \pi)_1}{(\Delta C)_1} = \frac{(\Delta \pi)_2}{(\Delta C)_2} \end{aligned}$$

or

$$\Delta \pi = \frac{1}{2} \Delta C \left(\frac{\Delta \pi_1}{\Delta C_1} + \frac{\Delta \pi_2}{\Delta C_2} \right) \quad \dots (11)$$

have also been used.

We now define reflection coefficients σ_1 and σ_2 for the solutes 1 and 2 respectively given by

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_1 &= \left[\frac{\Delta P}{\Delta \pi_1} \right]_{J_v=0, \Delta \pi_2=0} \\ &= - \frac{\left[\frac{(\bar{V}_s)_1}{(C_s^-)_1} \frac{\partial(J_s)_1}{\partial(\Delta\mu_s)_1} - \bar{V}_\omega^2 \frac{\Delta C}{2\Delta C_1} \frac{\partial J_\omega}{\partial \Delta \mu_\omega} \right]}{\left[(\bar{V}_s)_1^2 \frac{\partial(J_s)_1}{\partial(\Delta\mu_s)_1} + (\bar{V}_s)_2^2 \frac{\partial(J_s)_2}{\partial(\Delta\mu_s)_2} + \bar{V}_\omega^2 \frac{\partial J_\omega}{\partial \Delta \mu_\omega} \right]} \quad \dots (12) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_2 &= \left[\frac{\Delta P}{\Delta \pi_2} \right]_{J_v=0, \Delta \pi_1=0} \\ &= - \frac{\left[\frac{(\bar{V}_s)_2}{(C_s^-)_2} \frac{\partial(J_s)_2}{\partial(\Delta\mu_s)_2} - \bar{V}_\omega^2 \frac{\Delta C}{2\Delta C_2} \frac{\partial J_\omega}{\partial \Delta \mu_\omega} \right]}{\left[(\bar{V}_s)_1^2 \frac{\partial(J_s)_1}{\partial(\Delta\mu_s)_1} + (\bar{V}_s)_2^2 \frac{\partial(J_s)_2}{\partial(\Delta\mu_s)_2} + \bar{V}_\omega^2 \frac{\partial J_\omega}{\partial \Delta \mu_\omega} \right]} \quad \dots (13) \end{aligned}$$

Equation (10) using equation (11) may alternatively be written as

$$J_v = \left[\frac{\partial(J_s)_1}{\partial(\Delta\mu_s)_1} (\bar{V}_s)_1^2 + \frac{\partial(J_s)_2}{\partial(\Delta\mu_s)_2} (\bar{V}_s)_2^2 + \frac{\partial J_\omega}{\partial \Delta \mu_\omega} \bar{V}_\omega^2 \right] \Delta P + \left[\frac{\Delta C_1}{\Delta C} \cdot \frac{(\bar{V}_s)_1}{(C_s^-)_1} \frac{\partial(J_s)_1}{\partial(\Delta\mu_s)_1} + \frac{\Delta C_2}{\Delta C} \cdot \frac{(\bar{V}_s)_2}{(C_s^-)_2} \frac{\partial(J_s)_2}{\partial(\Delta\mu_s)_2} - \bar{V}_\omega^2 \frac{\partial J_\omega}{\partial \Delta \mu_\omega} \right] \Delta \pi \quad \dots (14)$$

The reflection coefficients, σ , may now be written as

$$\sigma = \left[\frac{\Delta P}{\Delta \pi} \right]_{J_v=0} = - \frac{\left[\frac{\Delta C_1}{\Delta C} \cdot \frac{(\bar{V}_s)_1}{(C_s^-)_1} \frac{\partial(J_s)_1}{\partial(\Delta\mu_s)_1} + \frac{\Delta C_2}{\Delta C} \cdot \frac{(\bar{V}_s)_2}{(C_s^-)_2} \frac{\partial(J_s)_2}{\partial(\Delta\mu_s)_2} - \bar{V}_\omega^2 \frac{\partial J_\omega}{\partial \Delta \mu_\omega} \right]}{\left[\frac{\partial(J_s)_1}{\partial(\Delta\mu_s)_1} (\bar{V}_s)_1^2 + \frac{\partial(J_s)_2}{\partial(\Delta\mu_s)_2} (\bar{V}_s)_2^2 + \frac{\partial J_\omega}{\partial \Delta \mu_\omega} \bar{V}_\omega^2 \right]} \quad \dots (15)$$

From equations (12), (13), and (15), it easily follows that

$$\sigma \Delta C = \sigma_1 \Delta C_1 + \sigma_2 \Delta C_2. \quad \dots (16)$$

For a general case when the solution contains any number of solutes it is, therefore, possible to write

$$\sigma \Delta C = \sum_i \sigma_i \Delta C_i. \quad \dots (17)$$

The volumetric flux, J_v , when permeating solutes and solvent interaction may be written as

It easily follows from equations (20), (22) and (23) that equation (17) holds good even in the present case wherein interaction between the permeating solutes and solvent is considered.

It is evident from equations (12), (13) and equations (22) and (23) that when permeation of solutes is completely checked, σ_1 and σ_2 are unity only when

$$\Delta C_1 = \Delta C_2 = \frac{\Delta C}{2}.$$

The reflection coefficient, σ , is however, unity when

$$(J_s)_1 = (J_s)_2 = 0.$$

$$J_v = \left[(\bar{V}_s)_1 \frac{\partial (J_s)_1}{\partial (\Delta \mu_s)_1} + (\bar{V}_s)_2 \frac{\partial (J_s)_2}{\partial (\Delta \mu_s)_1} + \bar{V}_\omega \frac{\partial J_\omega}{\partial (\Delta \mu_s)_1} + \right] (\Delta \bar{V}_s)_1 + \left[(\bar{V}_s)_1 \frac{\partial (J_s)_1}{\partial (\Delta \mu_s)_2} + (\bar{V}_s)_2 \frac{\partial (J_s)_2}{\partial (\Delta \mu_s)_2} + \bar{V}_\omega \frac{\partial J_\omega}{\partial (\Delta \mu_s)_2} \right] (\Delta \mu_s) + \left[(\bar{V}_s)_1 \frac{\partial (J_s)_1}{\partial \Delta \mu_\omega} + (\bar{V}_s)_2 \frac{\partial (J_s)_2}{\partial \Delta \mu_\omega} + (\bar{V}_\omega) \frac{\partial J_\omega}{\partial \Delta \mu_\omega} \right] \Delta \mu_\omega \quad \dots (18)$$

Using equations (9) and (11), above equation becomes

$$J_v = \left[(\bar{V}_s)_1^2 \frac{\partial (J_s)_1}{\partial (\Delta \mu_s)_1} + (\bar{V}_s)_2 (\bar{V}_s)_1 \frac{\partial (J_s)_2}{\partial (\Delta \mu_s)_1} + \bar{V}_\omega (\bar{V}_s)_1 \frac{\partial J_\omega}{\partial (\Delta \mu_s)_1} + (\bar{V}_s)_1 (\bar{V}_s)_2 \frac{\partial (J_s)_1}{\partial (\Delta \mu_s)_2} + (\bar{V}_s)_2^2 \frac{\partial (J_s)_2}{\partial (\Delta \mu_s)_2} + \bar{V}_\omega (\bar{V}_s)_2 \frac{\partial J_\omega}{\partial (\Delta \mu_s)_2} + (\bar{V}_s)_1 \bar{V}_\omega \frac{\partial (J_s)_1}{\partial \Delta \mu_\omega} + (\bar{V}_s)_2 \bar{V}_\omega \frac{\partial (J_s)_2}{\partial \Delta \mu_\omega} + \bar{V}_\omega^2 \frac{\partial J_\omega}{\partial \Delta \mu_\omega} \right] \Delta P + \left\{ \left[\frac{(\bar{V}_s)_1}{(C_s^-)_1} \frac{\partial (J_s)_1}{\partial (\Delta \mu_s)_1} + \frac{(\bar{V}_s)_2}{(C_s^-)_1} \frac{\partial (J_s)_2}{\partial (\Delta \mu_s)_1} + \frac{V_\omega}{(C_s^-)_1} \frac{\partial J_\omega}{\partial (\Delta \mu_s)_1} \right] \frac{\Delta C_1}{\Delta C} + \left[\frac{(\bar{V}_s)_1}{(C_s^-)_2} \frac{\partial (J_s)_1}{\partial (\Delta \mu_s)_2} + \frac{(\bar{V}_s)_2}{(C_s^-)_2} \frac{\partial (J_s)_2}{\partial (\Delta \mu_s)_2} + \frac{\bar{V}_\omega}{(C_s^-)_2} \frac{\partial J_\omega}{\partial (\Delta \mu_s)_2} \right] \frac{\Delta C_2}{\Delta C} - \left[(\bar{V}_s)_1 \bar{V}_\omega \frac{\partial (J_s)_1}{\partial \Delta \mu_\omega} + (\bar{V}_s)_2 \bar{V}_\omega \frac{\partial (J_s)_2}{\partial \Delta \mu_\omega} + \bar{V}_\omega^2 \frac{\partial J_\omega}{\partial \Delta \mu_\omega} \right] \right\} \Delta \pi \quad \dots (19)$$

$$\sigma = - \left\{ \frac{(\bar{V}_s)_1}{(C_s^-)_1} \frac{\partial (J_s)_1}{\partial (\Delta \mu_s)_1} + \frac{(\bar{V}_s)_2}{(C_s^-)_1} \frac{\partial (J_s)_2}{\partial (\Delta \mu_s)_1} + \frac{\bar{V}_\omega}{(C_s^-)_1} \frac{\partial J_\omega}{\partial (\Delta \mu_s)_1} \right\} \frac{\Delta C_1}{\Delta C} + \left\{ \frac{(\bar{V}_s)_1}{(C_s^-)_2} \frac{\partial (J_s)_1}{\partial (\Delta \mu_s)_2} + \frac{(\bar{V}_s)_2}{(C_s^-)_2} \frac{\partial (J_s)_2}{\partial (\Delta \mu_s)_2} + \frac{\bar{V}_\omega}{(C_s^-)_2} \frac{\partial J_\omega}{\partial (\Delta \mu_s)_2} \right\} \frac{\Delta C_2}{\Delta C} + \frac{\left[(\bar{V}_s)_1 \bar{V}_\omega \frac{\partial (J_s)_1}{\partial \Delta \mu_\omega} + (\bar{V}_s)_2 \bar{V}_\omega \frac{\partial (J_s)_2}{\partial \Delta \mu_\omega} + \bar{V}_\omega^2 \frac{\partial J_\omega}{\partial \Delta \mu_\omega} \right]}{\left\{ \left[(\bar{V}_s)_1^2 \frac{\partial (J_s)_1}{\partial (\Delta \mu_s)_1} + (\bar{V}_s)_2 (\bar{V}_s)_1 \frac{\partial (J_s)_2}{\partial (\Delta \mu_s)_1} + \bar{V}_\omega (\bar{V}_s)_1 \frac{\partial J_\omega}{\partial (\Delta \mu_s)_1} + (\bar{V}_s)_1 (\bar{V}_s)_2 \frac{\partial (J_s)_1}{\partial (\Delta \mu_s)_2} + (\bar{V}_s)_2^2 \frac{\partial (J_s)_2}{\partial (\Delta \mu_s)_2} + \bar{V}_\omega (\bar{V}_s)_2 \frac{\partial J_\omega}{\partial (\Delta \mu_s)_2} + (\bar{V}_s)_1 \bar{V}_\omega \frac{\partial (J_s)_1}{\partial \Delta \mu_\omega} + (\bar{V}_s)_2 \bar{V}_\omega \frac{\partial (J_s)_2}{\partial \Delta \mu_\omega} + \bar{V}_\omega^2 \frac{\partial J_\omega}{\partial \Delta \mu_\omega} \right] \right\}} \quad \dots (20)$$

Equation (19) may alternatively be written as

$$\begin{aligned}
 J_v = & \left[(\bar{V}_s)_1^2 \frac{\partial(J_s)_1}{\partial(\Delta\mu_s)_1} + (\bar{V}_s)_2(\bar{V}_s)_1 \frac{\partial(J_s)_2}{\partial(\Delta\mu_s)_1} + (\bar{V}_s)_1 \bar{V}_\omega \frac{\partial J_\omega}{\partial(\Delta\mu_s)_1} + (\bar{V}_s)_1(\bar{V}_s)_2 \frac{\partial(J_s)_1}{\partial(\Delta\mu_s)_2} + \bar{V}_\omega(\bar{V}_s)_2 \frac{\partial(J_s)_2}{\partial(\Delta\mu_s)_2} \right. \\
 & + (\bar{V}_s)_2 \bar{V}_\omega \frac{\partial(J_s)_1}{\partial(\Delta\mu_s)_2} + (\bar{V}_s)_2 \bar{V}_\omega \frac{\partial(J_s)_2}{\partial(\Delta\mu_s)_2} + (\bar{V}_s)_2 \bar{V}_\omega \frac{\partial(J_s)_2}{\partial(\Delta\mu_s)_2} + \bar{V}_\omega^2 \frac{\partial J_\omega}{\partial(\Delta\mu_s)_2} \left. \right] \Delta P + \left\{ \left[\frac{(\bar{V}_s)_1}{(C_s^-)_1} \frac{\partial(J_s)_1}{\partial(\Delta\mu_s)_1} \right. \right. \\
 & + \frac{(\bar{V}_s)_2}{(C_s^-)_1} \frac{\partial(J_s)_2}{\partial(\Delta\mu_s)_1} + \frac{\bar{V}_\omega}{(C_s^-)_1} \frac{\partial(J_\omega)}{\partial(\Delta\mu_s)_1} \left. \right] - \frac{\Delta C}{2\Delta C_1} \left[(\bar{V}_s)_1 \bar{V}_\omega \frac{\partial(J_s)_1}{\partial(\Delta\mu_s)_1} + (\bar{V}_s)_2 \bar{V}_\omega \frac{\partial(J_s)_2}{\partial(\Delta\mu_s)_1} + \bar{V}_\omega^2 \frac{\partial J_\omega}{\partial(\Delta\mu_s)_1} \right] \left. \right\} \Delta \pi \\
 & + \left\{ \left[\frac{(\bar{V}_s)_1}{(C_s^-)_2} \frac{\partial(J_s)_1}{\partial(\Delta\mu_s)_2} + \frac{(\bar{V}_s)_2}{(C_s^-)_2} \frac{\partial(J_s)_2}{\partial(\Delta\mu_s)_2} + \frac{\bar{V}_\omega}{(C_s^-)_2} \frac{\partial J_\omega}{\partial(\Delta\mu_s)_2} \right] - \frac{\Delta C}{2\Delta C_2} \left[\bar{V}_\omega(\bar{V}_s)_1 \frac{\partial(J_s)_1}{\partial(\Delta\mu_s)_2} + \bar{V}_\omega(\bar{V}_s)_2 \frac{\partial(J_s)_2}{\partial(\Delta\mu_s)_2} \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. + \bar{V}_\omega^2 \frac{\partial J_\omega}{\partial(\Delta\mu_s)_2} \right] \right\} \Delta \pi^2 \quad \dots (21)
 \end{aligned}$$

Thus,

$$\begin{aligned}
 \sigma_1 = & - \frac{\left[\frac{(\bar{V}_s)_1}{(C_s^-)_1} \frac{\partial(J_s)_1}{\partial(\Delta\mu_s)_1} + \frac{(\bar{V}_s)_2}{(C_s^-)_1} \frac{\partial(J_s)_2}{\partial(\Delta\mu_s)_1} + \frac{\bar{V}_\omega}{(C_s^-)_1} \frac{\partial J_\omega}{\partial(\Delta\mu_s)_1} - \frac{\Delta C}{2\Delta C_1} \left((\bar{V}_s)_1 \bar{V}_\omega \frac{\partial(J_s)_1}{\partial(\Delta\mu_s)_1} + \bar{V}_\omega(\bar{V}_s)_2 \frac{\partial(J_s)_2}{\partial(\Delta\mu_s)_1} \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. + \bar{V}_\omega^2 \frac{\partial J_\omega}{\partial(\Delta\mu_s)_1} \right) \right]}{\left[(\bar{V}_s)_1^2 \frac{\partial(J_s)_1}{\partial(\Delta\mu_s)_1} + (\bar{V}_s)_2(\bar{V}_s)_1 \frac{\partial(J_s)_2}{\partial(\Delta\mu_s)_1} + (\bar{V}_s)_1 \bar{V}_\omega \frac{\partial J_\omega}{\partial(\Delta\mu_s)_1} + (\bar{V}_s)_1(\bar{V}_s)_2 \frac{\partial(J_s)_1}{\partial(\Delta\mu_s)_2} + (\bar{V}_s)_2 \frac{\partial(J_s)_2}{\partial(\Delta\mu_s)_2} \right. \\
 & \left. + \bar{V}_\omega(\bar{V}_s)_2 \frac{\partial J_\omega}{\partial(\Delta\mu_s)_2} + (\bar{V}_s)_1 \bar{V}_\omega \frac{\partial(J_s)_1}{\partial(\Delta\mu_s)_2} + (\bar{V}_s)_2 \bar{V}_\omega \frac{\partial(J_s)_2}{\partial(\Delta\mu_s)_2} + \bar{V}_\omega^2 \frac{\partial J_\omega}{\partial(\Delta\mu_s)_2} \right]} \quad \dots (22)
 \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}
 \sigma_2 = & - \frac{\left[\frac{(\bar{V}_s)_1}{(C_s^-)_2} \frac{\partial(J_s)_1}{\partial(\Delta\mu_s)_2} + \frac{(\bar{V}_s)_2}{(C_s^-)_2} \frac{\partial(J_s)_2}{\partial(\Delta\mu_s)_2} + \frac{\bar{V}_\omega}{(C_s^-)_2} \frac{\partial(J_s)_1}{\partial(\Delta\mu_s)_2} - \frac{\Delta C}{2\Delta C_1} \left(\bar{V}_\omega(\bar{V}_s)_1 \frac{\partial(J_s)_1}{\partial(\Delta\mu_s)_2} + \bar{V}_\omega(\bar{V}_s)_2 \frac{\partial(J_s)_2}{\partial(\Delta\mu_s)_2} \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. + \bar{V}_\omega^2 \frac{\partial J_\omega}{\partial(\Delta\mu_s)_2} \right) \right]}{\left[(\bar{V}_s)_1^2 \frac{\partial(J_s)_1}{\partial(\Delta\mu_s)_1} + (\bar{V}_s)_2(\bar{V}_s)_1 \frac{\partial(J_s)_2}{\partial(\Delta\mu_s)_1} + (\bar{V}_s)_1 \bar{V}_\omega \frac{\partial J_\omega}{\partial(\Delta\mu_s)_1} + (\bar{V}_s)_1(\bar{V}_s)_2 \frac{\partial(J_s)_1}{\partial(\Delta\mu_s)_2} + (\bar{V}_s)_2 \frac{\partial(J_s)_2}{\partial(\Delta\mu_s)_2} \right. \\
 & \left. + (\bar{V}_s)_1 \bar{V}_\omega \frac{\partial J_\omega}{\partial(\Delta\mu_s)_2} + (\bar{V}_s)_1 \bar{V}_\omega \frac{\partial(J_s)_1}{\partial(\Delta\mu_s)_2} + (\bar{V}_s)_2 \bar{V}_\omega \frac{\partial(J_s)_2}{\partial(\Delta\mu_s)_2} + \bar{V}_\omega^2 \frac{\partial J_\omega}{\partial(\Delta\mu_s)_2} \right]} \quad \dots (23)
 \end{aligned}$$

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